

Effects of Averaging on Reaction Based Generalized Statistical Mechanics

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In previous notes, we argued that for both two body scattering and quantum systems, one may use generalized statistical mechanics using a physically determined function $g(f(e))$, $f(e)$ being the number of particles with energy e such that: $g(f(e)) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ where T is the temperature and u the chemical potential (here a normalization constant). For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $g=1$, for the Bose-Einstein (BE) case $g=f/(1+f)$ and for the Fermi-Dirac (FD) case $g=f/(1-f)$. In this note, we wish to examine two points. First, a reaction description does not seem to require large particle numbers in order to have an equilibrium. There is a catch to this, however, because at least in the Fermi Dirac situation where $(1-f(e))$ represents Pauli blocking, this blocking must be "physical Pauli blocking". If one has one electron jumping back and forth between two states, there is a probability $f(e)$ for it to be in one level or the other, but there is no Pauli blocking and one cannot use $(1-f(e))$. Thus, one may still use reaction balance for small numbers of fermions, but must be careful about the use of the factor $(1-f(e))$. We try to give examples to show how these issues occur.

Feynman Derivation of Bose-Einstein Distribution for Photons

In (1), Feynman derives the Bose Einstein distribution using the idea of a single electron jumping from a ground state to a first excited state and back. Photons are involved and he argues that if there are n photons in a state, the probability to add one more is $n+1$. Feynman uses the idea of balanced reactions to write:

$$(N \text{ ground state}) n = (n+1) (N \text{ first excited state}) \quad ((1))$$

Here n is the number of photons with energy $E \text{ first state} - E \text{ ground state}$. When an electron decays, it adds one more photon to the number n . Electrons are fermions and are subject to Pauli blocking, but there is no issue here because there is only one electron. Thus, Feynman argues that $N \text{ excited state} / N \text{ ground state} = \exp(-de/T)$ where de is the energy difference between the two states. ((1)) leads to the Bose Einstein distribution for photons.

We wish to argue four points here. First, statistical mechanical equilibrium has been applied to one electron. One does not need a large number of particles in order to have an equilibrium it seems. Secondly, only reaction balance has been used, no partition functions or entropy. Thirdly, no Pauli blocking occurs because there is only one electron. Fourthly, (1) does not seem to use energy conservation, but we think it is key because one may write:

$$(N \text{ ground}) \quad n/(1+n) = (N \text{ first excited}) \quad \text{and then take the ln:}$$

$$\ln(N_{\text{ground}}) + \ln(n/(1+n)) = \ln(N \text{ first excited}) \quad ((2))$$

This is of the form of a conservation equation and a solution is: $N_{\text{ground}} = \exp(-e_{\text{ground}}/T)$, $N_{\text{excited}} = \exp(-e_{\text{excited}}/T)$ and $\ln(n/(1+n)) = -de/T$ where $de = E_{\text{excited}} - E_{\text{ground}}$.

One may ask whether the above example may be modified to include the Pauli exclusion principle. This seems to be linked to a generalized statistical mechanical reaction approach. Instead of having one electron as in the above, imagine that there are many electrons, yet de is still the energy level between the ground state and the first excited state. Consider also that all other energy level spacings are different. Thus, a photon with energy de may only excite an electron from the ground state to the first excited state. Then, we use an average Pauli blocking value in ((1)) to write:

$$f(e_{\text{ground}}) n [1-f(e_{\text{first excited}})] = f(e_{\text{first excited}}) (n+1) [1-f(e_{\text{ground}})] \quad ((3))$$

We rewrite this as:

$$f(e_{\text{ground}}) / [1-f(e_{\text{ground}})] = n/(n+1) = f(e_{\text{first excited}}) / [1-f(e_{\text{first excited}})] \quad ((4))$$

Taking \ln of both sides and equating to energy conservation yields:

$$\ln\{ f(e) / [1-f(e)] \} = -(e-u)/T \quad \text{and} \quad \ln[n/(n+1)] = -de/T \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the first expression yields the Fermi-Dirac distribution for electrons, while the second the Bose-Einstein distribution for photons.

Thus, the Fermi-Dirac distribution occurs only if $1-f(e)$ is a reliable measure of Pauli blocking and this we think requires quite a few particles. A scenario of an electron dropping from e_1 to e_g and then moving from e_1 to e_g should not dominate the transactions because that does not cause Pauli blocking. If an electron is in e_g , there must be another electron in e_1 to create blocking. On the other hand, as seen above in the single electron example, one may have statistical mechanics with one electron, but its distribution is not the FD one. We wish to consider an example to try to clarify this.

Small Particle Number and Equilibrium

We wish to consider a system with two electrons interacting with a photon gas at temperature T . If the photons are in equilibrium, we assume they follow a Bose Einstein distribution. For simplicity, consider three equally spaced energy levels: the ground e_g , e_1 and e_3 . There will be Pauli blocking in such a case, but not enough we think to warrant a factor of $(1-f(e))$. Thus, we do not expect to have a FD distribution for the electrons. In a previous note (2), we considered this same case, but forced an FD distribution on the system. For such an FD (Fermi-Dirac) distribution to hold, we think more electrons are needed so that $(1-f(e))$ approximates Pauli blocking. As seen in the Feynman example of one electron, simply because there is a

probability to be in a ground state or excited state does not mean that there is blocking i.e. one cannot use a factor $(1-f(e))$ with one electron.

The scenarios in this example seem to be:

N1 cases of: 1 e1 0 eg 1 e3

N2 cases of 0e1 1eg 1e3

N3 cases of 1e1 1eg 0e3

Balance equations for e1 are: e3 to e1 (in) eg to e1 (in) e1 to e3 (out) e1 to eg (out)

$$N2(n+1) + n N2 = N3 n + (n+1) N1 \quad ((6))$$

Balance for eg: e1 to eg (in) e3 to eg (in) (jump of 2) eg to e1 (out) eg to e3 (out) jump of 2

$$(n+1) N1 + N1 (n2+1) = N2 n + N3 n2 \quad ((7))$$

where $n2$ is the BE distribution with energy $2de$ instead of de

Balance for e3: e1 to e3 (in) eg to e3 (in) (jump of 2) e3 to e1 (out) e3 to eg (out) jump of 2

$$n N3 + N3 n2 = N2 (n+1) + N1(n2+1) \quad ((8))$$

Let $N1=x$. One may then solve for $N2$ and $N3$ in terms of x . There are three equations above, so it may seem there is an inconsistency, but this does not seem to be the case

$$N1=x$$

$$N2 = x [n(n+2) + n2 (2n+1)] / [n*n + n2(2n+1)] \quad ((9))$$

$$N3 = N2 (2n+1)/n - (n+1)/n x \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Here: } n = 1/[1-\exp(-de/T)] \quad \text{and} \quad n2 = 1/[1-\exp(-2de/T)]$$

Thus, the ratio of particles in e1 to particles in n3 is:

$$F(e1) / F(e3) = [x+N3] / [x+N2] \quad ((11))$$

This does not seem to be a ratio of $f(\text{FD})(e1) / f(\text{FD})(e3)$ although an equilibrium still exists and Pauli blocking has been included.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that by using reaction balance, one may establish an equilibrium even for small numbers of particles by using reaction balance. In the case of fermions, however, one must be careful if one uses a Pauli blocking factor $(1-f(e))$, it must represent physical blocking. Thus, it seems the factor applies to cases where there are quite a few particles. For example, if there is only 1 particle switching from a ground state to an excited or 2 particles and three equally spaced energy levels, the Fermi-Dirac result does not seem to be achieved, even though there is Pauli blocking and reaction balance.

References

1. Feynman, R. Lecture Notes https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_04.html
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Scattering Balance Approach to Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)